

THE EFFECT OF RELIGIOSITY AND BRAND LOYALTY ON PURCHASE DECISIONS (Case Study at Aurel Hijab Shop in Lhokseumawe City)

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence of religiosity and brand loyalty on consumer purchasing decisions at the Aurel Hijab Store in Lhokseumawe City. This study uses a quantitative approach with a survey method. The research population is consumers of the Aurel Hijab Store, with a sample size of 100 respondents determined using the Lemeshow formula and convenience sampling techniques. Data collection was carried out through a structured questionnaire with a Likert scale, then analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) program through multiple linear regression analysis. The results of the study indicate that partially religiosity (X1) has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions (Y), as evidenced by a t-test with a significance value smaller than 0.05. This indicates that the higher the level of consumer religiosity, the stronger their tendency to make decisions to purchase hijab products that are in line with Islamic values. Furthermore, brand loyalty (X2) also has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions (Y) based on the t-test results, which indicates that consumer loyalty to the brand encourages repeat purchases and product recommendations. Simultaneously, the F-test results show that religiosity and brand loyalty together have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 76.4% indicates that variations in purchasing decisions can be explained by religiosity and brand loyalty, while the rest is influenced by other variables outside the research model. This finding confirms that consumer purchasing decisions for hijab are not only determined by brand loyalty, but also by the suitability of the product with the religious values held by consumers.

Keywords: Religiosity, Brand Loyalty, Purchasing Decisions

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia, the fourth most populous country in the world, is rich in cultural, ethnic, and religious diversity. With a population of over 270 million, Indonesia is home to various ethnic and religious groups. Of this number, approximately 87.2%, or more than 229 million, are Muslim, making Indonesia the country with the largest Muslim population in the world (Central Bureau of Statistics, 2020). This phenomenon not only reflects Indonesia's cultural diversity but also influences many aspects of people's lives, including consumer behavior. One area affected is the fashion industry, particularly the hijab, which is increasingly popular among Indonesian Muslim women. The hijab, which serves more than just a covering for Muslim women, has evolved into a symbol of identity, piety, and cultural expression in society. In recent years, awareness of the importance of wearing a hijab in accordance with Islamic principles has increased, accompanied by high demand for hijab products that are not only fashionable but also meet the criteria of modesty according to Islamic law. This condition has driven the rapid development of the hijab fashion industry in Indonesia, both in terms of the number of producers and consumers. Aurel Hijab Shop in Lhokseumawe City is one example that shows how the hijab business is growing to meet these needs. Lhokseumawe, a city in Aceh Province renowned for its adherence to Islamic law, has a highly religious population. This influences consumer consumption patterns, which consider not only the functional aspects of a product but also its suitability to their religious teachings. For consumers in Lhokseumawe, choosing a hijab is not just about style but also about its compliance with their Islamic values. Aurel Hijab, which offers hijabs that not only meet functional needs but also comply with Islamic law, is the right choice for consumers who prioritize product compliance with their religion. On the other hand, in the business world, brand loyalty also plays a crucial role in purchasing decisions. Brand loyalty reflects a consumer's deep commitment to a particular brand,

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which leads to repeat purchases. Loyal consumers tend to continue purchasing products from brands they trust, even when alternatives are available. In the context of Toko Aurel Hijab, brand loyalty is an equally important aspect, as consumers who are satisfied with the quality and value offered by the brand are more likely to make repeat purchases and recommend the product to others. Therefore, well-established brand loyalty can be a factor in strengthening Toko Aurel Hijab's position in this increasingly competitive market. Purchasing decisions, particularly in the hijab fashion industry, are the result of a series of considerations involving various factors. In addition to functionality and price, consumers also consider emotional and religious factors related to the products they will buy. Religiosity is one of the dominant factors in making hijab purchasing decisions. Consumers with a high level of religiosity tend to choose products that not only meet functional needs but also align with their religious teachings, as reflected in Islamic principles regarding modesty and modesty. Furthermore, brand loyalty also plays a significant role in purchasing decisions, where consumers who are loyal to a particular hijab brand are more likely to make repeat purchases. This study aims to analyze the influence of religiosity and brand loyalty on consumer purchasing decisions at the Aurel Hijab Store in Lhokseumawe City. By understanding the factors that influence these purchasing decisions, this study is expected to provide deeper insights for fashion industry players, especially hijab consumers, in designing effective marketing strategies. Considering that hijab consumers desire not only fashionable products but also products that align with religious values, this study will further examine how religiosity and brand loyalty contribute to purchasing decisions. In addition, this research is also expected to contribute to the development of marketing theory, especially in the context of Islamic products, as well as open opportunities for further research on consumer behavior in the hijab fashion industry.

The growing demand for Islamic-compliant hijabs has created a significant market potential for businesses in this sector. Amidst increasingly fierce competition, understanding consumer behavior driven by religiosity and brand loyalty is key to building lasting relationships between brands and consumers. Aurel Hijab Shop, with its approach that prioritizes product quality in accordance with Islamic teachings and builds brand loyalty, has a significant opportunity to strengthen its market position and increase its competitiveness. This research, focusing on Aurel Hijab Shop, will not only provide an understanding of the influence of religiosity and brand loyalty on purchasing decisions but also provide broader insights into how businesses can design marketing strategies focused on Muslim consumers who are increasingly discerning in choosing products that align with their religious teachings. As the hijab industry continues to grow rapidly, this research is expected to open opportunities for hijab businesses to innovate and adapt to increasingly complex consumer needs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Buying decision

A purchasing decision is the process consumers undertake to select and purchase a particular product. Factors influencing this decision include problem recognition, information search, alternative evaluation, and post-purchase behavior (Kotler & Armstrong, 2021). Purchasing decisions are influenced by functional and emotional aspects, including whether the product meets the consumer's needs and personal preferences (Andrian, 2022).

Religiosity

Religiosity refers to a person's level of attachment to their religion, encompassing beliefs, religious practices, and actions consistent with religious teachings (Hendriks et al., 2020). In the context of consumption, religiosity influences consumer preferences for products that align with their religious values, such as modesty and appropriateness in wearing the hijab (Sari, 2020).

Brand Loyalty

Brand loyalty is a consumer's commitment to a particular brand, reflected in repeat purchases of that brand's products, despite the presence of alternatives on the market (Kotler & Keller, 2021). Brand loyalty is influenced by positive experiences, satisfaction, brand image, and product quality that meets consumer expectations (Malik & Bhargaw, 2019). Brands that build emotional connections with consumers are more likely to maintain their loyalty.

The Influence of Religiosity and Brand Loyalty on Purchasing Decisions

Previous research has shown that religiosity and brand loyalty significantly influence purchasing decisions for Islamic products, such as hijabs. Religious consumers tend to choose products that align with their religious values, while brand loyalty can encourage repeat purchases and product recommendations (Sari, 2020; Hidayah &

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Sari, 2022). Research by Aisyah & Faizin (2024) also revealed that religiosity influences brand loyalty and purchasing decisions for hijab products.

METHOD

Types of research

This study used a quantitative approach with a survey method. It aimed to measure the influence of religiosity and brand loyalty on consumer purchasing decisions at the Aurel Hijab Store in Lhokseumawe City.

Population and Sample

Population: The population in this study are consumers who shop at the Aurel Hijab Shop in Lhokseumawe City.

Sample: This study sample consisted of 100 respondents, determined using the Lemeshow formula and a convenience sampling technique. The sample consisted of consumers aged 17-40 who had purchased hijab products at Toko Aurel between 2023 and 2024.

Research Variables

Independent Variables:

- Religiosity (X1): Consumer attitudes and behavior related to obedience and understanding of religious teachings that influence hijab purchasing decisions.
- Brand Loyalty (X2): Consumer loyalty to hijab brands that influences repeat purchasing decisions.

Dependent Variable:

- Purchase Decision (Y): Consumer decision to purchase hijab products from Aurel Hijab Shop.

Data collection technique

Data was collected through a questionnaire distributed to respondents. The questionnaire used a Likert scale to measure religiosity, brand loyalty, and purchasing decisions. The research instrument consisted of closed-ended questions that measured consumer attitudes and preferences.

Data analysis

The collected data will be analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software. This technique is used to test the partial and simultaneous effects of religiosity and brand loyalty on purchasing decisions.

Data Quality Test

- Validity Test: Using correlation between items with total scores, and the instrument is declared valid if the calculated r is greater than the table r .
- Reliability Test: Using the Cronbach's Alpha test to measure the internal consistency of the questionnaire. An instrument is considered reliable if the alpha value is greater than 0.6.

Classical Assumption Test

- Normality Test: Using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test to ensure that the data is normally distributed.
- Heteroscedasticity Test: Using a scatterplot graph to check for inequality of variance.
- Multicollinearity Test: Using tolerance values and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) to detect multicollinearity between independent variables.

Hypothesis Testing

- T-test: Used to test the influence of religiosity and brand loyalty on purchasing decisions partially.
- F-test: Used to test the simultaneous influence of religiosity and brand loyalty on purchasing decisions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

The purpose of this study was to determine the extent to which the independent variables, religiosity and brand loyalty, influence the dependent variable, purchasing decisions, both simultaneously and partially. In this

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study, the researchers used the *IBM SPSS 25 application* to analyze the multiple linear regression. The results are as follows:

Table 1 Results of Multiple Linear Regression Test

Variables	B	T count	Sig t	Information
(Constant)	2,344			
Religiosity	0.242	4,369	0.000	Significant
Brand Loyalty	0.599	8,205	0.000	Significant
F count	2,924			
Adjusted R squared	0.759			

Source: Data processed in 2025

From the results of the table above, the results of the multiple linear regression test obtained the following equation:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

$$Y = 2.344 + 0.242 X_1 + 0.599 X_2 + e$$

Information :

Y = Purchase decision

X1 = Religiosity

X2 = Brand loyalty

e = Other independent variables/residual error

These results indicate that each of the independent variables (religiosity and brand loyalty) influences purchasing decisions. The constant value is 2.344, indicating the value of the purchasing decision when all independent variables are set to zero.

1. Constant (α) = 2.344

If religiosity and brand loyalty have a value of 0, then the purchasing decision has a fixed value of 2.344.

2. The value of the regression coefficient of religiosity (X1) = 0.242

If the religiosity variable (X1) experiences an increase in value of one (1) point, then the purchasing decision will experience an increase of 0.242. Assuming the brand loyalty variable is considered constant. A positive coefficient means that there is a positive relationship between religiosity and purchasing decisions.

3. The value of the brand loyalty regression coefficient (X2) = 0.599

If the brand loyalty variable (X2) experiences an increase in value of one (1) point, then the purchasing decision will experience an increase of 0.599. Assuming the religiosity variable is considered constant.

Research Hypothesis Testing

A hypothesis is a temporary answer given by a researcher to each research problem statement. Hypothesis testing consists of H_a and H_o , which determine whether the research hypothesis will be accepted or rejected. Hypothesis testing has two methods: the F test (simultaneous) and the t test (partial).

1. F Test (Simultaneous)

The simultaneous test aims to determine whether independent variables together or simultaneously are able to influence the dependent variable. According to (Ghozali, 2018:98) the simultaneous test examines the overall regression line being studied, whether Y is linearly related to X1, X2, and X3. Researchers in conducting the test by comparing the calculated t value $\alpha = 0.05$. If the significance value is > 0.05 then it can be stated that there is no influence between the independent and dependent variables. Conversely, if the significance value is < 0.05 then it can be stated that there is an influence between the independent and dependent variables. The results of the simultaneous test in this study are as follows:

Table 2 Simultaneous Test Results (F Test)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
I	Regression	983,112	2	491,556	156,702	.000 ^b
	Residual	304,278	97	3,137		
	Total	1287,390	99			

Source: Data processed in 2025

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Based on the F-test results obtained from the ANOVA table, the calculated f-value of 156.702 with a significance value (p-value) of 0.000 indicates that the overall regression model has a significant contribution. This independent variable, namely religiosity and brand loyalty, can together significantly influence purchasing decisions because the value is smaller than 0.05, which means **Ha3 is accepted**.

2. t-Test (Partial)

The partial test aims to prove the influence of one independent variable in explaining the dependent variable. Rejection or acceptance of the hypothesis can be done by comparing the t-statistic value with the critical point value according to the table. An independent variable individually influences the dependent variable if the t-statistic value is higher than the t-table value (Ghozali, 2018:99). In decision making, if the significance value during the t-test is less than or <0.05 , it is stated that the independent variable has a significant effect on the dependent variable. Meanwhile, if the significance value is >0.05 , the hypothesis is rejected so that there is no influence between the pineapple variable partially and the dependent variable. The results of the partial test in this study are as follows:

Table 3 Partial Test Results (t-Test)

Model	<i>B</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Beta</i>	t count.	Sig.
1 (Constant)	2,344	0.802		2,924	0.004
Religiosity	0.242	0.055	0.323	4,369	0.000
Brand Loyalty	0.599	0.073	0.606	8,205	0.000

a. *Dependent Variable* : Purchase Decision

Source: Data processed in 2025

Based on the results of the t-test in multiple linear regression analysis, the interpretation of each independent variable on the dependent variable (purchase decision) is obtained by comparing the significance value in the calculated t-value with the t-table. The t-table value of 0.05 (5%) obtained from 100 respondents is 1.984. Therefore :

1. Religiosity

The calculated t-value for the religiosity variable is 4.369 with a significance value of 0.000. At a significance level of 5 percent, the t-table value of 1.984 indicates that religiosity has a positive effect on the decision. purchase. This means that the higher the level of consumer religiosity, the more big consumer the take decision For buy. Therefore **Ha1 is accepted**.

2. Brand Loyalty

The calculated t-value for the brand loyalty variable is 8.205 with a significance value of 0.000. At a 5 percent significance level, the t-table value of 1.984 indicates that brand loyalty has a positive influence on purchasing decisions. This means that the higher a consumer's brand loyalty, the greater their purchase intention. Therefore, **Ha2 is accepted**.

Correlation Coefficient

The correlation coefficient aims to measure the strength of the association between variables, thereby providing a more useful description of the data from those variables. The results of the correlation coefficient in this study are as follows:

Correlations

		X1	X2	Y
X1	Pearson Correlation	1	.744 **	.774 **
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	0.000
	N	100	100	100
X2	Pearson Correlation	.744 **	1	.847 **
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000
	N	100	100	100
Y	Pearson Correlation	.774 **	.847 **	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000	
	N	100	100	100

Source: Data processed in 2025

Based on the results of the Pearson correlation test, variables X1 and X2 have a significant positive relationship with variable Y. The correlation value between X1 and Y of 0.774 indicates that both have a strong and positive relationship, meaning that an increase in X1 tends to be followed by an increase in Y. Meanwhile, the correlation value between X2 and Y of 0.847 indicates a strong and positive relationship, where an increase in X2 is also followed by an increase in Y. Both relationships are statistically significant with a significance value of 0.000, which means that the relationship does not occur by chance and can be trusted.

1. Coefficient of Determination

The purpose of calculating the coefficient of determination is to illustrate how much variation can be explained in the model. There are two ways to measure the coefficient of determination: simultaneous determination and partial determination.

2. Simultaneous Determination Coefficient (R^2)

The simultaneous determination coefficient is used to measure the model's ability to describe the independent variables relative to the dependent variable. Researchers used *IBM SPSS 25* to view the simultaneous determination coefficients in the *model summary table* and used the *adjusted R-square* x 100% formula. The results of the simultaneous determination in this study are as follows:

Table 4 Results of Simultaneous Determination Coefficient (R^2) Test

<i>Model Summary</i> ^b				
<i>Model</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>R Square</i>	<i>Adjusted R Square</i>	<i>Standard Error of the Estimate</i>
1	.874 ^a	0.764	0.759	1.77113

Source: Data processed in 2025

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the R Square has a value of 0.764 or 76.4%. This indicates that 76.4% of the decision variables Purchases are explained by religiosity and brand loyalty variables. The remaining 23.6% is explained by factors other than those in the model.

3. Partial Determination Coefficient (r^2)

The purpose of the partial coefficient of determination is to determine the magnitude of the influence of each variable in this study. Partial determination is also used to determine the contribution of religiosity and brand loyalty to purchasing decisions. The results of the partial coefficient of determination in this study are as follows:

Table 5 Results of Partial Determination Coefficient Test (r^2)

<i>Model</i>	<i>Correlations</i>		
	<i>Zero-order</i>	<i>Partial</i>	<i>Part</i>
1 <i>(Constant)</i>			
Religiosity	0.774	0.406	0.216
Brand Loyalty	0.847	0.640	0.405

Source: Data processed in 2025

Based on the table above, all independent variables significantly influence purchasing decisions. Religiosity has a partial value. as big as 0.406 so his contribution is $(0.406)^2 \times 100\% = 16.4\%$. The brand loyalty variable has a partial value of 0.640, so its contribution is $(0.640)^2 \times 100\% = 40.9\%$.

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Religiosity on Purchasing Decisions (Case Study at Aurel Hijab Shop in Lhokseumawe City)

Based on the results of research conducted by researchers, it shows that the religiosity variable influences purchasing decisions. This is proven by the results of a partial hypothesis test (t-test) conducted by comparing the religiosity variable with purchasing decisions. Based on the t-test table, it can be seen that the religiosity variable (X1) has a calculated t value of 4.369 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, which means there is an influence between the religiosity variable and purchasing decisions or Ha1 is accepted. Furthermore, based on the results of the hypothesis test, namely the partial determination coefficient (r²) of the religiosity variable obtained a value of 16.4%. This statement proves that the higher the level of religiosity owned by consumers, the greater their tendency to make purchases, especially on products that are in accordance with religious values. This shows that religiosity is one of the important factors that influence consumer behavior in making purchasing decisions.

Research conducted by (Murdayana & Rokhman, 2025) shows that there is a significant and positive influence of the religiosity variable on purchasing decisions. This is supported by the results of research (Aula & Anwar, 2024) which shows that religiosity has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions as indicated by the calculated t value of $2.982 > t$ table 1.985 with a significance value of $0.004 \leq 0.05$. It can be concluded that there is an aspect of religiosity indicating that people still pay attention to religious principles when shopping. They consider various things in accordance with Islamic teachings, starting from the products purchased, the raw materials of the products, to the transaction methods used.

The influence of brand loyalty on purchasing decisions (case study at the Aurel Hijab shop in Lhokseumawe city)

Based on the results of research conducted by researchers, it shows that the brand loyalty variable influences purchasing decisions. This is proven by the results of a partial hypothesis test (t-test) conducted by comparing the brand loyalty variable with purchasing decisions. Based on the t-test table, it can be seen that the religiosity variable (X1) has a calculated t value of 8.205 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ which means there is an influence between the brand loyalty variable and purchasing decisions or Ha2 is accepted. Furthermore, based on the results of the hypothesis test, namely the partial determination coefficient (r²) of the brand loyalty variable obtained a value of 40.9%. This statement proves that Meaning, the higher the level of consumer loyalty to a brand, the greater they are to make repeat purchases or continue to choose products from that brand.

Research conducted by (Azhari et al., 2024) shows that there is a significant and positive influence of brand loyalty variables on purchasing decisions. This is supported by (Anggrainia, 2025) research results that show that brand loyalty has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions as indicated by the calculated t-value of 2.433 with a significance value of 0.018. It can be concluded that brand loyalty plays a significant role in influencing consumer purchasing decisions. The higher a consumer's loyalty to a brand, the more likely they are to make repeat purchases and continue to choose products from that brand. This finding reinforces the view that brand loyalty is a key factor in shaping consumer purchasing behavior.

The influence of brand loyalty religiosity on purchasing decisions (case study at the Aurel Hijab shop in Lhokseumawe City)

Based on the results of the research that has been conducted, it is proven that religiosity and brand loyalty together influence purchasing decisions positively and significantly. This is proven by simultaneous hypothesis testing (F test), the calculated f value of 156.702 with a significance value (p-value) of $0.000 < 0.05$ indicates that the overall regression model has a significant contribution. This means that the independent variables, namely religiosity and brand loyalty, can together influence purchasing decisions significantly because the significance value is smaller than 0.05, which means Ha4 is accepted. The results of this study align with (Aisyah & Faizin, 2024) that religiosity and brand loyalty have a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions. These findings indicate that consumers not only consider loyalty to brands they trust but also consider religious values in every purchasing decision they make. Thus, these two variables play a crucial role in shaping consumer behavior, particularly in the context of religiously tinged products such as hijabs. Therefore, businesses such as Toko Aurel

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Hijab are advised to not only maintain quality and brand image to remain consistent in the minds of consumers, but also prioritize religious values in their marketing strategies, such as providing halal-labeled products, using Islamic-themed promotions, and maintaining business ethics in accordance with sharia. These efforts are believed to increase customer trust and loyalty while encouraging sustainable purchasing decisions.

CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion that has been described, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Religiosity has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions at Aurel Hijab Shop in Lhokseumawe City. The higher a consumer's religiosity, the more likely they are to purchase products that align with their religious values.
2. Brand loyalty also has a positive and significant influence on in-store purchasing decisions. The more loyal consumers are to a brand, the more likely they are to purchase products from that brand again in the future.
3. Religiosity and brand loyalty together have a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions. This indicates that consumers consider not only brand loyalty but also the product's compatibility with their religious values.
4. The results showed that 76.4% of the variation in purchasing decisions can be explained by religiosity and brand loyalty. The remainder is influenced by other factors not examined in this study. In addition to maintaining quality and brand image, stores also need to emphasize religious aspects in their marketing strategies, such as using promotions aligned with Islamic values and maintaining business ethics consistent with religious teachings. These efforts are expected to increase customer trust and loyalty, as well as encourage sustainable purchasing decisions.

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